

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Modules 1-4

Representative questions for pre-test

Representative questions for post-test

Raw data tables 1-4

MODULE-1

PROTEINS

What are proteins?

Different types of proteins.

Different examples of proteins.

Functions of proteins.

How does proteins look like?

Knowing proteins *in silico*.

Protein data bank

<https://www.rcsb.org/>

The Protein Data Bank (PDB) is a database for the three-dimensional structural data of large biological molecules, such as proteins and nucleic acids.

Main window of PDB.

RCSB PDB

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NEW! Computed Structure Models (CSM) [Learn more](#)

Welcome

Deposit

Search

Visualize

Analyze

Download

Learn

RCSB Protein Data Bank (RCSB PDB) enables breakthroughs in science and education by providing access and tools for exploration, visualization, and analysis of:

- Experimentally-determined 3D structures from the **Protein Data Bank (PDB)** archive
- Computed Structure Models (CSM)** from AlphaFold DB and ModelArchive

These data can be explored in context of external annotations providing a structural view of biology.

COVID-19 CORONAVIRUS Resources

Join the RCSB PDB Team

October Molecule of the Month

Phytohormone Receptor DWARF14

Activate Windows
Go to PC settings to activate Windows.

Address [] 7:40 AM 19-Oct-22

Click on search to search different protein structures. We will search haemoglobin and insulin one by one and see how these look like.

MODULE-2

TRANSLATION

What is translation?

Process of translation.

Concept of codon.

Differences between prokaryotic and eukaryotic translation?

Knowing translation *in silico*.

National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) and Sequence Manipulation Suit (SMS)

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

<https://www.bioinformatics.org/sms2/>

NCBI main window

Main window of SMS

SMS Sequence Manipulation Suite:
Version 2

Format Conversion

- Combine FASTA
- EMBL to FASTA
- EMBL Feature Extractor
- EMBL Trans Extractor
- Filter DNA
- Filter Protein
- GenBank to FASTA
- GenBank Feature Extractor
- GenBank Trans Extractor
- One to Three
- Range Extractor DNA
- Range Extractor Protein
- Reverse Complement
- Split Codons
- Split FASTA
- Three to One
- Window Extractor DNA
- Window Extractor Protein

Sun 14 Jun 00:39:59 2020
Valid XHTML 1.0, Valid CSS

Sequence Analysis

- Codon Plot
- Codon Usage
- CpG Islands
- DNA Molecular Weight
- DNA Pattern Find
- DNA Stats
- Fuzzy Search DNA
- Fuzzy Search Protein
- Ident and Sim
- Multi Seq Trans
- Mutate for Digest
- ORF Finder
- Pairwise Align Codons
- Pairwise Align DNA
- Pairwise Align Protein
- PCR Primer Stats
- PCR Products
- Protein GRAVY
- Protein Isoelectric Point
- Protein Molecular Weight
- Protein Pattern Find
- Protein Stats
- Restriction Digest
- Restriction Summary
- Reverse Translate
- Translate

Sequence Figures

- Align
- Compare
- Dot Plot
- Histogram
- Logo
- Motif
- Phylogeny
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new window | home | citation

Activate Windows
Go to PC settings to activate Windows.

Address: https://www.bioinformatics.org/sms2/rev_comp.html

8:32 AM
19-Oct-22

Download coding sequence (CDS) of insulin gene from NCBI.

In silico translation: Translate this CDS in SMS and understand translation.

MODULE-3

ENZYMES

What is an enzyme?

Types of enzymes.

Nature of enzymes.

Mechanism of enzyme action.

Examples of enzymes.

Understanding enzyme activity *in silico*.

Virtual lab (v-lab) of Acharya Narendra Dev College (ANDC), University of Delhi, New Delhi

<https://www.vlab.andcollege.du.ac.in/>

Home page of v-lab

To perform an experiment to demonstrate the enzymatic activity of Trypsin on v-lab.

MODULE-4

BIOCHEMICAL TESTS

Test to detect protein.

Test to detect fat and lipid.

Test to detect starch.

Test to detect glucose.

Demonstration of biochemical tests *in silico*.

YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/>

Home page of YouTube

The screenshot shows a web browser window with multiple tabs open. The active tab is a YouTube search results page for the query "detection of starch by iodine test". The search results include an advertisement for Sigma-Aldrich's Potassium Iodide Starch P and two video results. The first video, titled "IODINE TEST OF STARCH(carbohydrates)", is by BIOS BIOME and has 44K views. The second video, titled "Iodine Test For Starch Practical Experiment", is by ThomasTKlungnung and has 56K views. The browser's address bar shows the URL "youtube.com/results?search_query=detection+of+starch+by+iodine+test". The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the time as 9:05 AM on 19-Oct-22.

To understand Iodine test, Xanthoproteic test, Sudan III test and Benedict's test *in silico*.

REPRESENTATIVE PRE-TEST QUESTIONS

1. What are codons?
2. Haemoglobin is made up of subunits.
3. Which test is commonly used to detect starch in a solution?
4. Identify following image.

5. Give examples of amino acids.
6. What is translation?
7. What is difference between DNA and RNA?
8. How do you know if a person is suffering from diabetes?
9. Write down a random DNA sequence?
10. What is a catalyst?

REPRESENTATIVE POST-TEST QUESTIONS

1. Refer the following DNA sequence:

AATGCCGATTGCCAGAGTT

- Demarcate codons in this sequence.
- Write complementary sequence of the above sequence.

2. Which of the following is the structure of haemoglobin?

a)

b)

c)

d)

3. What is the colour of starch solution after addition of Iodine?

a)

b)

c)

d)

4. Match the following single letter code with respective amino acids:

- | | |
|---|---------------|
| A | Tyrosine |
| Y | Tryptophan |
| W | Alanine |
| F | Phenylalanine |

5. What does following figure indicate:

6. A sample has very high concentration of glucose. Upon adding Benedict's reagent it turns into specific colour. Choose the colour.

- a)

7. Enzymes are:

- a) Proteins
- b) RNA
- c) Catalyst
- d) All of the above
- e) Only a and c is true

8. Write RNA sequence of the following DNA:

ATGCGCATTTCGGATCGG

9. Draw the structure of a ribosome and label its subunits.

10. A person is suffering from diabetes. Which test will you use to diagnose his pathological condition?

RAW DATA TABLE 1

Score of control group in pre-test based on questions of total 20 marks. Control group consists of 25 girls (serial number 1-25) and 25 boys (serial number 25-50).

S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks	S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks
1.	20	0	26.	20	0
2.	20	4	27.	20	0
3.	20	4	28.	20	0
4.	20	4	29.	20	0
5.	20	2	30.	20	0
6.	20	4	31.	20	0
7.	20	0	32.	20	2
8.	20	0	33.	20	2
9.	20	0	34.	20	2
10.	20	0	35.	20	2
11.	20	4	36.	20	2
12.	20	10	37.	20	2
13.	20	4	38.	20	0
14.	20	4	39.	20	0
15.	20	6	40.	20	4
16.	20	2	41.	20	4
17.	20	2	42.	20	8
18.	20	8	43.	20	10
19.	20	4	44.	20	2
20.	20	4	45.	20	2
21.	20	4	46.	20	2
22.	20	4	47.	20	2
23.	20	4	48.	20	2
24.	20	4	49.	20	2
25.	20	4	50.	20	2

RAW DATA TABLE 2

Score of experimental group in pre-test based on questions of total 20 marks. Experimental group consists of 25 girls (serial number 1-25) and 25 boys (serial number 25-50).

S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks	S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks
1.	20	4	26.	20	2
2.	20	2	27.	20	2
3.	20	2	28.	20	2
4.	20	2	29.	20	4
5.	20	2	30.	20	4
6.	20	0	31.	20	2
7.	20	0	32.	20	2
8.	20	0	33.	20	0
9.	20	0	34.	20	0
10.	20	0	35.	20	0
11.	20	4	36.	20	0
12.	20	4	37.	20	0
13.	20	2	38.	20	0
14.	20	2	39.	20	0
15.	20	8	40.	20	0
16.	20	10	41.	20	8
17.	20	2	42.	20	2
18.	20	4	43.	20	2
19.	20	4	44.	20	4
20.	20	6	45.	20	4
21.	20	4	46.	20	4
22.	20	8	47.	20	0
23.	20	8	48.	20	0
24.	20	4	49.	20	6
25.	20	4	50.	20	2

RAW DATA TABLE 3

Score of control group in post-test based on questions of total 20 marks. Control group consists of 25 girls (serial number 1-25) and 25 boys (serial number 25-50).

S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks	S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks
1.	20	8	26.	20	2
2.	20	12	27.	20	4
3.	20	6	28.	20	4
4.	20	8	29.	20	6
5.	20	8	30.	20	4
6.	20	8	31.	20	4
7.	20	4	32.	20	4
8.	20	4	33.	20	4
9.	20	4	34.	20	4
10.	20	4	35.	20	8
11.	20	4	36.	20	10
12.	20	8	37.	20	8
13.	20	8	38.	20	8
14.	20	12	39.	20	4
15.	20	10	40.	20	8
16.	20	10	41.	20	10
17.	20	8	42.	20	4
18.	20	14	43.	20	2
19.	20	2	44.	20	2
20.	20	2	45.	20	6
21.	20	4	46.	20	4
22.	20	8	47.	20	8
23.	20	2	48.	20	8
24.	20	2	49.	20	4
25.	20	8	50.	20	4

RAW DATA TABLE 4

Score of experimental group in post-test based on questions of total 20 marks. Experimental group consists of 25 girls (serial number 1-25) and 25 boys (serial number 25-50).

S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks	S.No.	Full marks	Scored marks
1.	20	10	26.	20	10
2.	20	16	27.	20	10
3.	20	14	28.	20	10
4.	20	10	29.	20	8
5.	20	8	30.	20	8
6.	20	8	31.	20	8
7.	20	8	32.	20	8
8.	20	8	33.	20	12
9.	20	8	34.	20	8
10.	20	10	35.	20	10
11.	20	10	36.	20	8
12.	20	10	37.	20	12
13.	20	12	38.	20	14
14.	20	12	39.	20	14
15.	20	10	40.	20	12
16.	20	16	41.	20	12
17.	20	16	42.	20	10
18.	20	18	43.	20	10
19.	20	12	44.	20	10
20.	20	8	45.	20	12
21.	20	8	46.	20	12
22.	20	12	47.	20	12
23.	20	14	48.	20	14
24.	20	12	49.	20	10
25.	20	12	50.	20	12